

Experimental / BIM Extended

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API Version: 1.0.0

Manage the BIM entities not integrated in the service Mature / BIM Sync.

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API

1. PERSONS

1.1 GET /persons

List Persons

List GUIDs of all the persons.

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
[string]
```

1.2 PUT /persons

Put Person

Register the person with the service based on its GUID.

REQUEST

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{  
  Represent a person involved with the system.  
  guid*  string  PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$  
           Generally unique identifier (GUID) of the person  
  email* string  PATTERN:^[^@]+@[^[@.,,]+](\.[^@.,,])*$  
           E-mail address of the person  
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
undefined
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc*  [string]  
    msg*  string  
    type* string  
  }]  
}
```

1.3 GET /persons/{guid}

Get Person

Get the data of the specified person.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-]+\$</code>	GUID of the person

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  Represent a person involved with the system.  
  guid*  string  PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$  
           Generally unique identifier (GUID) of the person  
  email* string  PATTERN:^[^@]+@([^. , ]+)(\.[^@. , ])*$  
           E-mail address of the person  
}
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc*  [string]  
    msg*  string  
    type* string  
  }]  
}
```

1.4 DELETE /persons/{guid}

Delete Person

Unregister the person from the service and delete all the related data.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-]+\$</code>	GUID of the person

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

1.5 HEAD /persons/{guid}

Head Person

Check whether the person has been registered with the service.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_:-]+\$</code>	GUID of the person

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: The person has been registered with the service.

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 404: The person has not been registered.

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

2. TASKS

2.1 GET /tasks

List Tasks

List GUIDs of all the tasks.

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

[string]

PATTERN: `^[a-zA-Z0-9_ . :-]+$`

2.2 PUT /tasks

Put Task

Register the task with the service based on its GUID.

REQUEST

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{
```

Represent a task on a construction site.

<code>guid*</code>	<code>string</code>	PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_ . :-]+\$</code>
		Generally unique identifier (GUID) of the task
<code>name*</code>	<code>string</code>	Human-readable name of the task
<code>long_description*</code>	<code>string</code>	Longer description of the task
<code>subtasks*</code>	[string]	PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_ . :-]+\$</code>
<code>scheduled_start*</code>	<code>integer</code>	Scheduled start of the task (seconds since epoch in UTC)
<code>scheduled_end*</code>	<code>integer</code>	Scheduled end of the task (seconds since epoch in UTC)
<code>related_products*</code>	[{	
	Array of object: Represent a building element.	
<code>guid*</code>	<code>string</code>	PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_ . :-]+\$</code>
		Generally unique identifier (GUID) of the building element
<code>revision_url*</code>	<code>string</code>	URL to the revision of the building plan (*e.g.*, in BIM Sync)
<code>url*</code>	<code>string</code>	URL to the more information about the building element (*e.g.*, in BIM Sync)
	}]	
	}	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
```

```

detail [{
  Array of object:
    loc*   [string]
    msg*   string
    type*  string
  }]
}

```

2.3 GET /tasks/{guid}

Get Task

Get the data of the specified task.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$</code>	GUID of the task

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```

{
  Represent a task on a construction site.
  guid*           string           PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
                  Generally unique identifier (GUID) of the task
  name*           string           Human-readable name of the task
  long_description* string         Longer description of the task
  subtasks*       [string]        PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
  scheduled_start* integer         Scheduled start of the task (seconds since epoch in UTC)
  scheduled_end*  integer         Scheduled end of the task (seconds since epoch in UTC)
  related_products* [{
    Array of object: Represent a building element.
    guid*         string           PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
                  Generally unique identifier (GUID) of the building element
    revision_url* string           URL to the revision of the building plan (*e.g.*, in BIM Sync)
    url*          string           URL to the more information about the building element (*e.g.*, in BIM Sync)
  }]
}

```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```

{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc*   [string]
      msg*   string
      type*  string
    }]
}

```

2.4 DELETE /tasks/{guid}

Delete Task

Unregister the task from the service and delete all the related data.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$</code>	GUID of the task

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
    loc* [string]
    msg* string
    type* string
  }]
}
```

2.5 HEAD /tasks/{guid}

Head Task

Check whether the task has been registered with the service.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$</code>	GUID of the task

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: The task has been registered with the service.

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 404: The task has not been registered.

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```

{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}

```

2.6 GET /tasks/{guid}/statuses

List Task Statuses

List GUIDs of all the taks statuses.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$</code>	GUID of the task

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```

[string]
PATTERN: ^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$

```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```

{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}

```

2.7 PUT /tasks/{guid}/statuses

Put Task Status

Register the task status with the service based on its GUID.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$</code>	GUID of the task

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{
  guid*      string  PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
              Generally unique identifier (GUID) of the task status
  task_guid* string  PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
              GUID of the corresponding task
  timestamp* integer  Timestamp when the status was observed (seconds since epoch in UTC)
  status*    enum    ALLOWED:STARTED, IN_PROGRESS, FINISHED, STALLED, WAITING, CANCELLED
              Status of the task as observed at timestamp
  progress   number  between 0 and 100
              Percentage of the work done as observed at timestamp
  notes      string  Any notes regarding the task at timestamp
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
    loc*   [string]
    msg*   string
    type*  string
  }]
}
```

2.8 GET /tasks/{guid}/statuses/{status_guid}

Get Task Status

Get the data of the specified task status.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: ^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$	GUID of the task
*status_guid	string PATTERN: ^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$	GUID of the task status

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  guid*      string  PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
              Generally unique identifier (GUID) of the task status
```

```

task_guid* string  PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
                GUID of the corresponding task
timestamp* integer Timestamp when the status was observed (seconds since epoch in UTC)
status*   enum    ALLOWED:STARTED, IN_PROGRESS, FINISHED, STALLED, WAITING,
                CANCELLED
                Status of the task as observed at timestamp
progress  number  between 0 and 100
                Percentage of the work done as observed at timestamp
notes     string  Any notes regarding the task at timestamp
}

```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```

{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}

```

2.9 DELETE /tasks/{guid}/statuses/{status_guid}

Delete Task Status

Unregister the task status from the service and delete all the related data.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: ^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$	GUID of the task
*status_guid	string PATTERN: ^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$	GUID of the task status

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```

{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}

```

2.10 HEAD /tasks/{guid}/statuses/{status_guid}

Head Task Status

Check whether the task status has been registered with the service.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+</code>	GUID of the task
*status_guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+</code>	GUID of the task status

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: The task status has been registered with the service.

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 404: The task status has not been registered.

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

3. UXVS

3.1 GET /uxvs

List Uxvs

List GUIDs of all the UxVs.

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

[string]

PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+\$

3.2 PUT /uxvs

Put Uxv

Register the UxV with the service based on its GUID.

REQUEST

REQUEST BODY - application/json

```
{
  Represent an unmanned vehicle.
  guid*      string  PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+$
                Generally unique identifier (GUID) of the unmanned vehicle
  kind*      enum    ALLOWED:UGV, UAV
                Represent the kind of an unmanned vehicle.
  name*      string  Human-readable name of the vehicle
  description* string Human-readable (longer) description of the vehicle
  image_url* string  URL to the image symbolizing the vehicle. It can also be in-lined, *e.g.*, as base64-encoded image.
}
```

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
    loc*   [string]
    msg*   string
    type*  string
  }]
}
```

3.3 GET /uxvs/{guid}

Get Uxv

Get the data of the specified UxV.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+\$</code>	GUID of the UxV

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  Represent an unmanned vehicle.  
  guid*      string  PATTERN:^[a-zA-Z0-9_~.-]+$  
              Generally unique identifier (GUID) of the unmanned vehicle  
  kind*      enum    ALLOWED:UGV, UAV  
              Represent the kind of an unmanned vehicle.  
  name*      string  Human-readable name of the vehicle  
  description* string Human-readable (longer) description of the vehicle  
  image_url* string  URL to the image symbolizing the vehicle. It can also be in-lined, *e.g.*, as base64-encoded image.  
}
```

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{  
  detail [{  
    Array of object:  
    loc* [string]  
    msg* string  
    type* string  
  }]  
}
```

3.4 DELETE /uxvs/{guid}

Delete Uxv

Unregister the UxV from the service and delete all the related data.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_-:~]+\$</code>	GUID of the UxV

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```

3.5 HEAD /uxvs/{guid}

Head Uxv

Check whether the UxV has been registered with the service.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
*guid	string PATTERN: <code>^[a-zA-Z0-9_.-]+</code>	GUID of the UxV

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: The UxV has been registered with the service.

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

STATUS CODE - 404: The UxV has not been registered.

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
  detail [{
    Array of object:
      loc* [string]
      msg* string
      type* string
    }]
}
```
